

Research Article

Analytical Method Development And Validation For The Estimation Of Azelnidipine In Bulk Drug And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

The current study covers the invention of an isocratic RP-HPLC method that is straightforward, affordable, quick, accurate, and precise for estimating the amount of bulk azelnidipine and in its commercial products. An evaluation was conducted at 260 nm, which was determined to be Azelnidipine's λ_{max} . The Cosmosil C18 Column, measuring 250 mm by 4.6 mm and 5 μ m, was used to establish the straightforward, isocratic, and selective RP-HPLC method for azelnidipine. The mobile phase was made up of methanol at pH 6 with 1% formic acid with OPA Water (58: 42% V/V) with a 1.0 ml/min flow rate and 260 nm detecting wavelength. ICH Q2 (R1) requirements were successfully followed in the validation of the developed approach. With r^2 values of 0.9996, the chromatographic techniques demonstrated an excellent linear response. The approaches were determined to be precise when there was less than a two percent relative standard deviation. It was possible to infer from the findings that the established approach was robust, selective and specific. The examination of bulk azelnidipine and its commercial formulation could be effectively conducted using this technology.

INTRODUCTION

Hydrophobicity is the basis for molecular separation in RP-HPLC. Outstanding resolution that is achievable in a variety of chromatographic settings [1]. It is possible to control chromatographic selectivity by altering the properties of the mobile phase. Excellent production and quick recoveries. Outstanding repeatability of repeated separations performed

over an extended length of time. A new dihydropyridine derivative that acts antagonistically against calcium (Fig. 1). Azelnidipine has only been measured using a few number of analytical techniques, such as HPLC, LC-MS, and LC-ESI-MS [2-4].

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50 µg/ml) in HPLC and on various days. Typically, standard deviation are used to express it [14-16].

Robustness:

Using a 30-µg/ml solution of Azelnidipine, the mobile phase composition was changed in a proportion and the varied in detection wavelength (±1 ml/min-1) [14].

Limit of Detection & Quantification:

The following formula was used to determine LOD and LOQ in accordance with ICH regulations. $LOQ = 10 \times \sigma / S$ and $LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma / S$ [14-18].

RESULT & DISCUSSION:

Method Development for Azelnidipine By RP-HPLC

The mobile phase flowed one milliliter each minute. 20 µl was the injection volume and the wavelength used was 260 nm. The sample and column temperatures were at room temperature. The 15-minute sample run produced a chromatogram that was deemed good, and the system suitability parameters were acquired correctly. Enhanced chromatographic conditions (Fig.2) and system suitability parameters were developed.

Figure 2: UV Spectrum for Azelnidipine

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

The mobile phase that was chosen and optimized was Methanol : (1% formic Acid)pH 6 with OPA Water (58: 42% V/V) and Parameters optimized were the wavelength (260 nm), flow rate (1.0

ml/minute), and run time (15 minutes). Better results were displayed by the separated peaks in this instance. It was determined that the suggested chromatographic conditions (Fig. 3) were suitable for the drug's quantitative determination.

Figure 3: Chromatogram of Azelnidipine in Optimized Condition

Linearity

Linearity was assessed at 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentrations. Figure 4 displays the Azelnidipine

calibration graph. Table 2, displays the linearity

Figure 4: Calibration curve of Azelnidipine for HPLC method

Table 1: Linearity of Azelnidipine

Sr. No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area
1	10	305.68
2	20	718.48
3	30	1140.14
4	40	1606.42
5	50	2036.72

Accuracy

Accuracy was assessed in the range of 80-120% of sample (table 3). The accuracy of the analytical method expressed as % recovery determines the

degree of closeness between the obtained and the true values. The overall % recovery was observed to be in the range of 99-101% for Azelnidipine (Figure 5).

Table 2: Details of Accuracy

Accuracy	% Recovery
80%	101.36
100%	98.20
120%	99.97

Figure 5 (a): Chromatogram of Accuracy 80%

Figure 5 (b): Chromatogram of Accuracy 100%

Figure 5 (c): Chromatogram of Accuracy 120%

Precision

Precision is expressed as % RSD, and % RSD NMT 2% is considered acceptable. Since the % assay and % RSD results were well within the

acceptable range. The proposed method was found to have an overall % RSD for intraday and inter-day precision of less than 2% (table 4).

Table 3 Results of Precision

Conc. (µg/ml)	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Mean (n=6)	% RSD	Mean (n=6)	% RSD
10	295.78	0.96	293.32	0.96
30	1141.87	1.10	1134.36	1.41
50	2043.14	0.83	2040.99	6.14

Robustness

Small and purposeful changes to chromatographic conditions and assay settings were made to test this. These modifications affected system appropriateness and injection results for standard and sample solutions. Table 5 shows that

wavelength and flow rate adjustments had no influence on retention time, theoretical plate, or asymmetry. %RSD should be LT 2%. This indicated that the analytical approach was reliable and the created approach also satisfied the restrictions.

Table 4: Results for Robustness

Parameter Used for Sample Analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time [min]	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor	%RSD
Mobile phase composition-(57+43)	2004.18	4.000	6825	0.80	0.14
Mobile phase composition-(59+41)	2015.61	4.278	6573	0.82	0.17
Wavelength change 259nm	2081.26	4.475	6733	0.81	0.21
Wavelength Change 261 nm	2084.42	4.267	6913	0.81	0.14
Flow rate change(0.9ml)	2350.96	5.039	6945	0.81	0.62
Flow rate change(1.1ml)	1764.15	3.779	6945	0.81	0.44

LOD and LOQ

$LOD = 3.3(Sy / S) = 3.3 \times 2.27/43.5 = 0.1722\mu\text{g/ml}$

$LOQ = 10(Sy / S) = 10 \times 2.27/43.5 = 0.5218\mu\text{g/ml}$

The values obtained for the LOD and LOQ indicated that the method was susceptible to detecting and quantifying the drug.

CONCLUSION

In this suggested development study, a straightforward, exact and accurate RP-HPLC method was established for the determination of Azelnidipine. The new HPLC method is simple to use, has a significantly shorter run time, and requires less time to prepare solutions. In order to optimize chromatography, all of the chromatographic parameters were tuned for a reliable and sturdy analytical approach. The approach was verified in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, and repeatability in accordance with legal standards and the suggested methodology by the ICH. The validation data demonstrates that the RP-HPLC method is sensitive, accurate, precise, specific, and repeatable, and that the devised method has acceptable repeatability. The suggested technique can be applied to Azelnidipine routine analysis and

quality control tests in medication samples and dosage forms. Since this approach may be simply adapted to estimate Azelnidipine in a variety of biological materials, it is advised for use in future bioanalytical analyses. The Azelnidipine method that was created is easy to use, quick, affordable, and suitable for industrial application.

REFERENCES

- Buralla, K. K., & Varadarajan P. (2020). Validated RPHPLC Method Development of Pazopanib HCl in Bulk and its Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *Pharmaceutical Methods*, 11(1), 21-24.
- Chaitanya, G., & Pawar. A. K. M. (2015). Development and Validation of UV spectrophotometric method for the determination of Pazopanib hydrochloride in bulk and tablet formulation. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 7(12), 219-225.
- Escudero-Ortiz, V., Pérez-Ruixo, J. J., & Valenzuela, B. (2015). Development and validation of an HPLCUV method for pazopanib quantification in human plasma and application to patients with cancer in routine clinical practice. *Therapeutic Drug Monitoring*, 37(2), 172–179.

- <https://doi.org/10.1097/FTD.0000000000000121>
- Ghode, P. D., Dhaigude, P. U., Rathod, S. P., Sayare, A. S., Pachauri, A. D., Khandelwal, K., & Ghode, S. P. (2020). Stability Indicating HPTLC Method Development and Validation for the Estimation of Pazopanib HCL in Bulk and its Dosage Form. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 12(3). <https://doi.org/10.31838/ijpr/2020.12.03.518>
 - Koylu, B., Tekin, F., Aktas B. Y., Kilickap, S., & Koksak. D. (2022). Pazopanib HCl - induced chylothorax in a patient with renal cell carcinoma. *Anti-Cancer Drugs*, 33(1), 555-557. <https://doi.org/10.1097/CAD.0000000000001172>
 - Ma, B., & Gou, X. L. (2016). Application of highperformance liquid chromatography in food and drug safety analysis. *Journal of Food Safety and Quality*, 7, 295-4298.
 - Minocha, M., Khurana, V., & Mitra, A. K. (2012). Determination of pazopanib (GW-786034) in mouse plasma and brain tissue by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC/MS-MS). *Journal of Chromatography. B, Analytical Technologies in the Biomedical and Life Sciences*, 901, 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2012.06.004>
 - Pressiat, C., Huynh, H. H., Plé, A., Sauvageon, H., Madelaine, I., Chougnet, C., Le Maignan, C., Mourah, S., & Goldwirt, L. (2018). Development and Validation of a Simultaneous Quantification Method of Ruxolitinib, Vismodegib, Olaparib, and Pazopanib in Human Plasma Using Liquid Chromatography Coupled with Tandem Mass Spectrometry. *Therapeutic drug Monitoring*, 40(3), 337–343.
 - Patil SD, Bachhav RS, Udavant PB, Ahirrao SP. Deepak S.bhambere4, Development and Validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method for Azelnidipine for bulk drug. *Natl Volatiles Essent Oils*. 2021;8(5):11151-7.
 - Gore MG, Pratap S. Dabhade, RP-HPLC method development and validation of azelnidipine, Gore and Dabhade, *IJPSR*. Vol. 7(12); 2016. p. 5111-4.
 - Prabhakar D, Sreekanth J, Jayaveera KN. Method development and validation of azelnidipine by RP-HPLC. *Int J ChemTech Res*. 2017;10(10):418-23.
 - Ubale S, Dr. Kalshetti MS, Habib B, Mittha J, Adlinge S. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for quantification of azelnidipine in tablet. *Int J Creat Res Thoughts (IJCRT)*. 2021;9 (7, July): 797-802.
 - Jadhav, Lokhande, Narwade, Mahananda V. Ghodke, Rutuja. S. Desai and Prerna R. Mote, Method development & validation of stability indicating Rp-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation for azelnidipine & telmisartan in bulk & pharmaceutical dosage form, *world. J Pharm Med Res Wjpmr*. 2022;8(3):216-22.
 - Zou Jian-Jun, et al, Determination of Azelnidipine by LC-ES-MS and its application to a pharmacokinetic study in healthy Chinese volunteers, *Pharmazie* 63, 2008, 568-570.
 - Nilam Patel, et al, Spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous determination of Azelnidipine and Olmesartanmedoxomil by First Derivative Spectrophotometric method, *Scholar Research Library*, 2012, 1080-1084.
 - Hiroyuki Daikuhara, et al, The combination of Olmesartan and a Calcium Channel Blocker (Azelnidipine) or candesartan and a Calcium Channel Blocker (Amlodipine) in Type 2 Diabetic hypertension patients: The OLCA study, *Diabetes and Vascular Disease Research*, 2012, 280-286.

17. Kunti D. Raskapur, et al, UV Spectrophotometric method development and validation for determination of Azelnidipine in pharmaceutical dosage form, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, Volume-4, Issue 1, 2012, 238-240.
18. Raveendra Babu Ganduri, Stability indicating liquid chromatographic method for determination of Olmesartan Medoxomil and Azelnidipine in combined Tablet dosage form, *International Journal of Pharma Science and Research*, Volume-5, 2014, 275-282.
19. Jayvadan K. Patel Validated stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the Simultaneous determination of Azelnidipine and Olmesartan in their combined dosage form, *Sci Pharm*, 2014, 541- 554
20. Rele Rajan V. Spectrophotometric estimation of Azelnidipine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form by second order derivative method, *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2014, 198-202.
21. Selvadurai Muralidharan, et al. Simple validation of Azelnidipine by RP-HPLC Method, AIMST University, Malaysia, Volume-1, 2015, 43-45.
22. Rajan V. Rele, et al., Development and validation of Stability Indicating Reverse Phase Liquid Chromatographic method for the assay of Azelnidipine in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation , *International Journal of Pharma and biosciences*, 2016, 270-275.
23. Prabhakar D., et al., Development and Evaluation of Transdermal Patches of Azelnidipine, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, Volume-5, 2013, 805.
24. Sethi P.D., et al., HPLC-Quantitative analysis of Pharmaceutical formulations, CBS publisher, & distributors, New Delhi, 2011, 11.
25. Yuri Kazakevich, Rosario Lobrutto, HPLC for Pharmaceutical Scientists, A John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Publication, Canada, 2007, 10-22, 26-34.
26. F. Settle, et al., Handbook of Instrumental Techniques for Analytical Chemistry, NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1997, 58.
27. Validation of Analytical procedure; Text and methodology Q2 (R1), International Conference on Harmonisation of technical requirements for human use, ICH Harmonized tripartite guidelines, 2005.
28. P. Ravisankar et al, A Review on Analytical Method Development, *Indian Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Biotechnology*. 2014, 1183-1195.
29. Kiyoshi Kawabata, et al. Simultaneous determination of Azelnidipine and two metabolites in human plasma using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry, *Drug metabolism and pharmacokinetics*, Resaerch Laboratories Sankyo, Co. Ltd. 1- 2- 58, Hiromachi, Shingawa-ku, Tokyo, Japan, 2006, 46-52.

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